

ARTICLE TOPIC: CENTRAL ASIAN CITIES ON THE SILK ROAD: INTERPLAY OF TRADITION AND MODERNITY

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Abstract. *Silk Road: The historic trade network that connected the East and the West, facilitating the exchange of goods, ideas, and cultures between Asia and Europe. Uzbekistan's focus on improving the tourism sector, developing infrastructure, and organizing tourist services according to international standards. Samarkand, Uzbekistan: An ancient city in Uzbekistan, known for its rich cultural and architectural monuments, attracting tourists from around the world. Service improvement. Enhancing and providing services at archaeological sites, heritage sites, and museums is crucial for attracting tourists and creating a positive tourism experience. Educational, digital, administrative, investment, security, and health services contribute to preserving cultural heritage and stimulating private sector investment.*

Key words: *Silk Road, Central Asia, Samarkand, exchange of goods, exchange of knowledge, cultural cross-pollination, modernization of tourism industry. Samarkand, UNESCO World Heritage List, tourist potential, tourism statistics, tourism infrastructure, modernization efforts, service improvement.*

INTRODUCTION

The Silk Road is the historic trade network that connected the East and the West across the continents of Asia and Europe. The Silk Road extended through several countries, including Central Asia. Some key cities in Central Asia that were part of the Silk Road:

Samarkand, Uzbekistan: Samarkand was the capital of the Timurid Empire and one of the largest commercial and cultural cities in Central Asia during the Middle Ages. It served as an important center for trade and cultural exchange along the Silk Road.

Bukhara, Uzbekistan: Bukhara is the capital of Uzbekistan and a historical city that dates back thousands of years. It was a vital commercial center on the Silk Road and the seat of successive empires such as the Samanids, Khwarazmians, and Timurids.

Kashgar, China: Located in East Central Asia, Kashgar was an important city on the Silk Road. It served as a thriving commercial and cultural hub and a major stop for traders and travelers along the route.

The Silk Road served as a bridge between East and West, connecting civilizations across vast distances. It allowed for the exchange of goods such as silk, spices, precious metals, ceramics, and textiles, but it also fostered the exchange of knowledge, ideas, and beliefs. Central Asian cities played a crucial role as hubs along the Silk Road, attracting merchants, scholars, and travelers from various cultures and regions. These cities became melting pots of diverse traditions, where different languages, religions, and artistic expressions converged.

The Silk Road was not only a route for the exchange of goods but also a channel for the transmission of ideas, cultures, and religions. Central Asian cities along the Silk Road played a crucial role in facilitating this exchange and became vibrant centers of commerce, culture, and intellectual pursuits. These Central Asian cities on the Silk Road witnessed a constant interplay between tradition and modernity. While they embraced new ideas, technologies, and trade

opportunities, they also preserved their rich cultural heritage. The architectural wonders, ancient traditions, and artistic expressions that flourished in these cities are a testament to their historical significance and the enduring legacy of the Silk Road.

Central Asian cities were not only centers of trade and intellectual pursuits but also places of cultural cross-pollination. The bazaars and marketplaces bustled with activity, where traders from different regions gathered to exchange goods, stories, and ideas. These interactions contributed to the blending of cultures, the emergence of new artistic forms, and the enrichment of local traditions.

Today, these cities continue to attract visitors from around the world, who come to explore their historical sites, bazaars, and museums, and to experience the vibrant blend of tradition and modernity that characterizes Central Asia along the Silk Road.

Uzbekistan places particular emphasis on the modernization of the tourism industry, the development and improvement of the regulatory framework for the sustainable development of the industry, and the organization of tourist services in accordance with international standards. The efforts of the leadership of the Republic of tourism infrastructure in recent years raised to a fairly high level. The measures taken to support and protect the private sector contributed to the increase in the number of tourist organizations and hotel facilities. There are 1,667 tourist organizations successfully operating in the country, including 989 tour operators and 869 hotel facilities. An extensive network of hotels with more than 25,000 beds meets modern international standards. For the period 2015-2017, the export of tourist services grew by 33% and amounted to USD 546.9 million in 2017, and for 9 months of 2018 - USD 773.4 million, exceeding the figures of 2017 in total by 41%. over 2 million people from different parts of the world visit the country annually. The number of arriving foreign visitors to Uzbekistan is growing at a high rate every year. **(1)**

Samarkand

Samarkand, which is rich in ancient cultural and architectural monuments, are important for the development of tourism in Uzbekistan and raising it to new levels. This city have ancient historical monuments that amaze and amaze people all over the world. Everyone living in different countries of the world dreams of seeing this city. The main purpose of the inclusion of historical monuments in the UNESCO World Heritage List is to promote and protect the world-famous sites in the region. It is known that Uzbekistan is a country rich in historical and cultural monuments **(2)**.

Samarkand is one of the most ancient cities of the world. It is situated deep in Central Asian interludes (39°40'N 67°00' E) **(Fig. 1)**, in the oasis of the Zarafshan River. This is the only large city of the world that history's three greatest generals: Alexander the Great, Chingiz-khan and Temur personally fought to make it their own**(3)**.It is one of the most important historical and archaeological landmarks in this city such as The town of Afrosiab (VIII century BC), Ulugbek Observatory (observatory) (1424- 1428), Shohi Zinda architectural complex (XI-XX centuries),

(1) A. Kucharov , ANALYSIS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN Associate Professor Kh. Ochilova Tashkent State University of Economics, “Иқтисодий ва инновацион технологиялар” илмий электрон журнали. № 2, март-апрель, 2019 йил, P 2-5.

(2) Ibdova Ezoza Anvarovna, Uzbek State University of World Languages, **Normuminova Ramila Maqsud qizi**, First-year students of the Faculty of Foreign Languages and Literature, **Burieva Iroda Ergashevna**, first-year student at the Faculty of English Philology, HISTORICAL AND ARCHITECTURAL HISTORY OF SAMARKAND REGION MONUMENTS AS OBJECTS OF EXCURSION , JournalNX- A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal, VOLUME 8, ISSUE 5, May. -2022,P10.

(3) Aleksey Arapov, Historical Monuments of Uzbekistan. New Edition, Tashkent: SMI-ASIA, 2017, P72.

Hazrati Hizr Mosque (middle of the XIX century), Bibihanim mosque (1399), Registan Square (1417-1647), Ruhabad mausoleum (1380), The Oqsaroy Mausoleum (1451-1469), Tomb of Amir Temur (1404), The mausoleum of Ishratkhana (1464), Khoja Ahrori Wali complex (XV-XX centuries), Tomb of Chopon-Ota (1430), Khoja Abdu Darun Cemetery (15th century), Cemetery of Khoja Abdu Berun (XVII century), Imam al-Bukhari complex (IX-XX centuries), Makhdumi Azam complex (XVI-XIX centuries), Tomb of Khoja Daniel (1870-1880).

(Fig. 1) A map illustrating the cities many routes of the ancient Silk Road. Credit... Map by Daniel Wagner

More than 460 objects of cultural heritage are concentrated in the territory of the city, mainly within the boundaries of the historical-architectural reserve. They are officially registered and protected by the state. There are many hotels, tourist companies, restaurants, shops, banks, and medical centers in the central area. Radiality prevails in the planning composition, there is a high need for the main streets to be renovated, greened and beautified, as well as to further expand their width in their current state. The city territory is provided with electricity, natural gas, centralized water supply and sewerage networks(4).

If we analyze the work done in the Samarkand tourism destination in January-December 2019, in January-December 2019, a total of 3,120,000 tourists visited the region, including 560,000 foreign tourists from 154 foreign countries. which is an increase of 1.59 times compared to the corresponding period of 2018. The number of local tourists also reached 2,560,000, which is 1.2 times more than in 2018.

Looking at the existing tourist potential of Samarkand, in January-December 2019, a total of 161 accommodation facilities (1239 rooms, 2841 places) were launched: 33 hotels, 128 family hotel houses,

Today in Samarkand there are 296 accommodation facilities, including 109 hotels (2388 rooms, 5238 beds), 151 family guest houses (589 rooms, 1362 beds), 29 hostels (250 rooms, 738 seats), 5 guest houses (31 rooms, 88 seats), 2 boutique hotels (68 rooms, 132 seats). In addition, 243 tourist vehicles, including 93 minibuses, 124 buses and 20 electric cars, 174 tour operators

(4)Chorshanbaev Fayzulla Ziyatovich, Melieva Chinnigul Otaqulovna, Ziyatova Aziza, URBAN PLANS IN THE AREA OF SAMARKAND CITY, GOSPODARKA I INNOWACJE, Volume: 34 | 2023, Economy and Innovation,P206.

and 230 guide-interpreters provide tourist services to local and foreign citizens. In the tourism destination of Samarkand in 2019, 9 tourist information centers for foreign and domestic tourists were established, 76 standard sanitary-hygienic outlets were built, road signs leading to 65 tourist facilities, 55 tourist facilities were built. A Wi-Fi zone has been set up.

In addition, representatives of the Samarkand region demonstrated the tourism potential of the region at international exhibitions in Italy, China, India, Finland, Latvia, Russia, the United Arab Emirates, Germany and Ukraine. (5).

One of the most important manifestations of interest in the infrastructure of the city of Samarkand is as part of modernity and contemporaneity that serves the nature of the historical city. We can find the following :

- Ongoing construction of a new road of modern tourist infrastructure facilities (hotels, hotels, boarding houses, restaurants, cafes, transport, etc.) to the Grebnoy Channel.
- Organization of unique, attractive for tourists cable cars/cruises on the historical sites of the city.
- The use of exotic special Religious tours to study the multicultural ideological ties of the city.
- The formation of common territorial recreational systems along the rivers (after their restoration) under the name "Golden Heritage and Historical Landscape of Samarkand" and "The Great Path to the Tomb of the Prophet Daniel".
- Activation of the development of tourism infrastructure in the historical environment.
- Creation of a network of ethnographic national parks and reserves;
- The formation of local tourist centres in all three historical parts, including the ancient part of the city.
- Development of communication infrastructure, seamless Internet.
- the introduction of innovative spaces in tourist routes, archaeological and pale ontological excursions, theatrical ethnographic events, traditional sports competitions and games, folklore events.
- Organization of new winter routes, ecological tourism, museums of new profiles.
- Expansion of recreational areas, health-improving areas through the development of natural areas of the city.
- Construction of new entertainment establishments and tourist centres along the Zaravshan River using unique natural resources.
- Completion of the construction of highways and bridges outside the historical zone.
- putting into operation new modern objects of tourist infrastructure - hotels, restaurants and other entertainment and play facilities within the boundaries of the historical zone in the outskirts of the city
- Activation of sports tourism; - development of the ecological direction in tourism due to the pristine corners of nature.
- The introduction of new forms (camel caravans, helicopters, cycling for complex excursions).
- Organization of adventure tourism, exotic ethnographic and religious tours.

(5) **Rakhimov Zafar Odilovich**, SAMARKAND TOURISM DESTINATION: STATUS AND DEVELOPMENT,

Associate Professor of Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service. Republic of Uzbekistan, European Scholar Journal (ESJ), Vol. 2 No. 2, February 2021, ISSN: 2660-5562 , P 62-63.

- Organization of rural, mountain tourism.
- -Development of archaeological tourism. (6)

Air Marakanda modernizes the international airport "Samarkand" improving the spaces surrounding archaeological sites

Samarkand Railway Station Improving visitor services at archaeological sites

Improving and providing services in Samarkand

Improving and providing services for visitors at archaeological sites, heritage sites, and museums in Samarkand is a fundamental factor that helps attract tourists and visitors. It contributes to enhancing cultural awareness and achieving an enjoyable and educational visit experience. Furthermore, it preserves cultural heritage and enhances the quality of tourist services, which has the greatest impact on creating a positive mental image for tourists and visitors and improving their tourism experience. This encourages them to repeat their visits multiple times because enhancing the tourism experience is one of the main pillars of tourism development, achieving sustainable development goals, and promoting efforts to protect and preserve cultural heritage while stimulating private sector investment.

Examples of these services include:

1. **Educational services** such as informational panels, maps, brochures, and visitor centres.
2. **Digital services** such as virtual reality (VR), augmented reality (AR), and mobile applications.
3. **Administrative services** such as infrastructure rehabilitation, restrooms, shades, seating areas, and ticket offices.
4. **Investment services** such as gift shops, restaurants, cafeterias, and audiovisual services.

(6) Sultanov Damir Utkurovich, "Modernization And Development Of Old Tourist Routes In Samarkand", INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SCIENTIFIC & TECHNOLOGY RESEARCH VOLUME 11, ISSUE 01, JANUARY 2022, ISSN 2277-8616, P71.

5. **Security services** such as inspection offices, fences, and security personnel.
6. **Health services** such as emergency clinics.

Visitor services in the Prince Timur Complex, the Ruhobot Complex and the city's public roads

CONCLUSION

The Silk Road served as a historic trade network connecting Asia and Europe, with Central Asian cities playing a vital role as hubs along the route. Cities like Samarkand, Bukhara, and Kashgar were centers of commerce, culture, and intellectual pursuits, fostering the exchange of goods, knowledge, and beliefs. These cities were melting pots of diverse traditions, where different cultures and artistic expressions converged. The Silk Road not only facilitated trade but also contributed to the blending of cultures and the enrichment of local traditions. Today, these cities continue to attract visitors from around the world, offering a blend of historical sites, vibrant bazaars, and a glimpse into the enduring legacy of the Silk Road. Uzbekistan, in particular, has made significant efforts to modernize its tourism industry, developing infrastructure, supporting the private sector, and meeting international standards. The growth in tourist services and the increasing number of visitors to Uzbekistan reflect the continued interest in exploring the historical significance and cultural heritage of Central Asia along the Silk Road.

Samarkand, with its ancient cultural and architectural monuments, plays a significant role in the development of tourism in Uzbekistan. The city's inclusion in the UNESCO World Heritage

List highlights its importance and promotes the preservation of its renowned sites. Samarkand's tourist potential is vast, with numerous historical and archaeological landmarks, attracting millions of visitors each year. The city has seen a steady increase in tourism, both from foreign and local tourists. To accommodate the growing number of visitors, the tourism infrastructure has been expanding, including the establishment of accommodation facilities, tourist vehicles, and service providers. Efforts to modernize the city and its tourism industry are underway, focusing on improving infrastructure, introducing new attractions, and developing communication networks. Moreover, enhancing services at archaeological sites and heritage sites is a crucial aspect of providing a positive tourism experience and preserving cultural heritage. Samarkand's commitment to improving services and infrastructure reflects the country's dedication to promoting tourism and attracting visitors from around the world.

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